

RUBEANIC ACID AND ITS DERIVATIVES AS COLORIMETRIC REAGENTS. PART IV. *NN'*-DIBENZYL- AND *NN'*-DIPHENYL-RUBEANIC ACIDS

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The use of *NN'*-dibenzyl- and *NN'*-diphenyl-rubeanic acids as colorimetric reagents for certain elements of the transitional series is reported. *NN'*-Dibenzylrubeanic acid gives metallic complexes almost similar to those of the parent compound, but with lower solubilities in common organic solvents. However, the aryl derivative (*NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid), though highly coloured, can be used with equal or even greater advantage than rubeanic acid itself for the colorimetric determination of copper, nickel, cobalt and palladium. The reagent has been found to be more sensitive than its parent compound or its alkyl analogues. For comparison, the behaviour of monothio-oxanilide towards various metallic cations has also been studied.

The effect of substitution in the amido groups of rubeanic acid by alkyl radicals in respect of the usefulness of those products as colorimetric reagents has been described in the earlier part of this series (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 633). In the present paper a study of similar substitution by groups containing aromatic rings has been presented. The low solubility of *NN'*-dibenzylrubeanic acid as well as of its metallic complexes in organic solvents seems to furnish an evidence of the pronounced weighting effect of the substituent. This makes the reagent unsuitable for the direct determination of metallic cations. On the other hand, *NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid and its metallic complexes are sufficiently soluble in organic solvents to permit its use as a very suitable reagent for the spectrophotometric estimation of copper, cobalt, nickel and palladium. It is found to be more sensitive than its parent compound or its alkyl analogues. As the colour of most of the metal complexes of *NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid can be readily extracted from their aqueous pyridine solution by *isobutyl* or *isoamyl* alcohol, the methods of colorimetric estimation with this reagent can be further refined and made more effective by such extractions. For, it can be used for estimating concentration of metal ions much lower than what is possible of estimation in aqueous pyridine solution. Monothio-oxanilide, which is related closely to *NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid (dithio-oxanilide), has been found, however, much less effective as a reagent for analytical purposes. The colour of its metallic compounds is rather weak and dull, besides being unstable.

EXPERIMENTAL

NN'-Dibenzylrubeanic Acid ($C_6H_5 \cdot CH_2 \cdot NH \cdot CS \cdot CS \cdot NH \cdot CH_2 \cdot C_6H_5$)

The compound was prepared by warming rubeanic acid with an alcoholic solution of benzylamine (Wallach and Reinhardt, *Annalen*, 1891, 262, 354). The properties of metal-*NN'*-dibenzylrubeanates are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Metal.	Properties.
Copper (II)	Greenish black precipitate (from neutral, ammoniacal or weakly acetic acid solution); very difficultly soluble in most of the common organic solvents.
Cobalt (II)	Deep brown precipitate with a yellow tinge (from ammoniacal solution); somewhat soluble in pyridine, but very sparingly soluble in other organic solvents. The orange-yellow pyridine solution is extractable by toluene.
Nickel (II)	Deep violet-pink precipitate (from ammoniacal solution); fairly soluble in acetone, benzene, chloroform, ethyl or amyl acetate, isoamyl or isobutyl alcohol and more easily in pyridine (deep violet colour, extractable by isoamyl or isobutyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate, toluene or chloroform). But the pyridine solution is unstable, turning turbid in a short time.
Palladium (II)	Orange-yellow precipitate (from ammoniacal solution); soluble in acetone, chloroform, ethyl or amyl acetate and pyridine (yellow colour, extractable by toluene, benzene, etc.). But the solution in these solvents rapidly turns turbid.
Silver (I)	Pale yellow precipitate (from neutral solution).
Gold (III)	Same as above (acid solution).
Platinum (IV)	Orange-yellow coloration (from acid solution).
Lead (II)	Yellow-white precipitate (from neutral solution).

Spot Tests.—The spot tests of copper, cobalt, nickel and palladium, using *NN'*-dibenzylrubeanic acid were carried out in a manner analogous to that with other substituted rubeanic acids (*loc. cit.*). The identification and concentration limits for different metals are recorded below:

Cu : 0.107 (1 : 5 × 10⁵).

Co : 0.0357 (1 : 1.4 × 10⁶).

Ni : 0.047 (1 : 1.25 × 10⁵).

Pd : 0.067 (1 : 5 × 10⁵).

NN'-Diphenylrubeanic Acid (C₆H₅-NH-CS-CS-NH-C₆H₅)

NN'-Diphenylrubeanic acid was obtained along with monothio-oxanilide (C₆H₅-NH-CS-CO-NH-C₆H₅) by the action of phosphorus pentasulphide on oxanilide (Reissert, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3720). Dithio-oxanilide crystallises out from glacial acetic acid as shining reddish yellow plates, m.p. 133-34°. Monothio-oxanilide forms pure yellow crystals, m.p. 144-45°.

The properties of the metallic complexes of *NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid and monothiooxanilide are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Metal.	<i>NN'</i> -Diphenylrubeanic acid (Dithio-oxanilide) (I)	Monothio-oxanilide (II)
Copper (II)	Yellowish green precipitate (from neutral, ammoniacal or weakly acetic acid solution); sparingly soluble in most of the common organic solvents; easily soluble in pyridine (greenish yellow colour, extractable with <i>iso</i> amyl or <i>iso</i> -butyl alcohol).	Light brown precipitate (from neutral, ammoniacal or weakly acetic acid solution); soluble in most of the common organic solvents; pyridine solution is coloured yellow.
Cobalt (II)	Orange-brown precipitate (from ammoniacal solution); easily soluble in benzene, toluene, chloroform, etc., but sparingly soluble in acetone; soluble in pyridine (orange-yellow colour, extractable with <i>iso</i> amyl or <i>isobutyl</i> alcohol).	Brown precipitate (from ammoniacal solution); slightly soluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform, etc.; easily soluble in pyridine (yellow colour).
Nickel (II)	Deep violet precipitate (from ammoniacal solution); sparingly soluble in alcohol (hot), acetone, <i>iso</i> amyl or <i>isobutyl</i> alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate; easily soluble in pyridine (pink-red colour, extractable with <i>iso</i> amyl or <i>isobutyl</i> alcohol).	Orange-yellow precipitate (from ammoniacal solution); sparingly soluble in benzene, alcohol, chloroform, etc.; easily soluble in <i>iso</i> amyl or <i>isobutyl</i> alcohol and pyridine (yellow colour).
Palladium (II)	Deep red precipitate (from acid solution); easily soluble in most of the common organic solvents; the orange-yellow pyridine solution is extractable with <i>iso</i> amyl or <i>isobutyl</i> alcohol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and ethyl or amyl acetate.	Orange-yellow precipitate (from acid solution); soluble in most of the common organic solvents (orange-yellow colour).
Platinum (IV)	Brownish red unstable precipitate (from acid solution).	Yellow colour (from acid soln.).
Gold (III)	Orange-red unstable precipitate (from acid solution).	Orange-yellow colour (from acid solution).
Silver (I)	Yellow precipitate (from neutral solution); stable towards dilute acids, but dilute alkali decomposes it; slightly soluble in organic solvents.	No precipitate or colour.
Bismuth (III)	Yellow precipitate (from acid solution), changing to brown and finally black.	Do
Lead (II)	Yellow precipitate (from neutral solution), decomposed by acids.	Do
Cadmium (II)	Pale yellow precipitate (from neutral solution), decomposed by acids.	Do

Spot Tests.—A very dilute alkaline ($N/100$) solution of the reagent was used for testing copper, cobalt and nickel. Palladium was detected in slightly acid solution. Identification and concentration limits are: Cu, 0.10γ ($0:10^5$); Co, 0.10γ ($1:10^6$); Ni, 0.40γ ($1:5 \times 10^5$) and Pd, 0.20γ ($1:5 \times 10^5$).

FIG. 1

*Absorption curves.**NN'*-Diphenylrubeanic acid metallic complex. Cell length = 10 mm.

Curve I—6 p.p.m. Cu. Curve II—1.45 p.p.m. Co. Curve III—2 p.p.m. Ni. Curve IV—2 p.p.m. Pd.

Spectrophotometric Determinations.—Based on the solubility of metal *NN'*-diphenylrubeanates in pyridine, spectrophotometric methods of determining copper, cobalt, nickel and palladium have been developed. Copper was determined by measuring the optical density of the greenish yellow solution at 420 $m\mu$; cobalt from the optical density of its orange-yellow colour at 410 $m\mu$; nickel from that of its pinkish red colour at 510 $m\mu$ and palladium from that of its yellow colour at 395 $m\mu$. The colour systems in all the cases were found to obey Beer's law.

Determination of Copper

The following solutions were used: Standard copper solution, 0.05 mg. Cu/c.c. Reagent solution, prepared by mixing equal volumes of a 0.1% alcoholic solution of *NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid and an aqueous solution (approximately 1*N*) of sodium hydroxide. The reagent solution was used after about half an hour from its preparation. Disodium versenate solution, 1% aqueous.

Absorption maximum (in the ultraviolet region).—The optical density of the complex solution is almost constant between 380 and 420 $m\mu$ (cf. Curve: I, Fig. 1). Measurements were made at 420 $m\mu$.

Pyridine concentration: 5 c.c. of pyridine in a total volume of 25 c.c. made up with water.

Reagent concentration: Maximum colour intensity was developed by 1 c.c. of the reagent solution, when the copper concentration did not exceed 0.20 mg.

Alkali concentration: Varying amounts of sodium hydroxide (from 1 c.c. of 0.1N to 10 c.c. of 1N) solution were added after the addition of the reagent solution. It was observed that the colour intensity remained unaltered, when measured against a reagent blank containing an equal quantity of sodium hydroxide.

Beer's Law.—The system obeys Beer's law (cf. Curve I, Fig. 2).

FIG. 2

Beer's law curves.

NN'-Diphenylrubeanic acid metallic complex. Cell length = 10 mm.

Curve I—Copper; 420 m μ . Curve II—Cobalt; 410 m μ . Curve III—Nickel; 510 m μ ; Palladium; 395 m μ .

Stability of the colour.—A solution containing 2 p.p.m. Cu remained clear without any appreciable change in its optical density for more than 24 hours. But when the copper content was about 10 p.p.m., a slight opalescence was noticed after 5-6 hours.

Sensitivity: 0.01 γ Cu/cm² (Sandell) and 0.08 γ Cu/cm² (practical).

Effect of diverse ions.—Cations that are precipitated, either by the alkaline reagent solution or by pyridine, interfere with the estimation of copper. However, disodium versenate (disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetra-acetic acid) has been found to be a suitable sequestering agent for many cations. The colour intensity of the copper *NN'*-diphenylrubeanate is unaffected by the addition of the versenate. The following ions were masked for 2 p.p.m. Cu by the addition of 1% aqueous solution of versenate:

Co^{2+} (50 γ), Ni^{2+} (50 γ), Pb^{2+} (500 γ), Cd^{2+} (400 γ), Cr^{3+} (100 γ), molybdate (200 γ), tungstate (200 γ) and Sn^{2+} (20 γ). Even when present in very small amounts, the following ions interfere: Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ag^+ , Au^{3+} , Pt^{4+} and Pd^{2+} .

Procedure.—To the test solution, containing preferably less than 0.3 mg. copper, 5 c.c. pyridine and 5 c.c. of 1% aqueous solution of disodium versenate were added. The volume was roughly adjusted to 20 c.c. with distilled water and treated with 1 c.c. of the alkaline reagent solution. A greenish yellow colour developed almost instantaneously. The volume was then made up to 25 c.c. with distilled water, and the optical density of the solution was measured at 420 $m\mu$, against a reagent blank which contained also the same amount of alkali as the sample solution.

Determination of Cobalt

The following solutions were used: Standard cobalt solution, 0.025 mg. Co/c.c. Reagent solution, prepared by mixing equal volumes of an alcoholic solution of *NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid (0.1%) and an aqueous solution (approx. *N/2*) of sodium hydroxide; 1% aq. sodium acetate solution, 5% (aqueous) potassium cyanide solution; and freshly distilled pyridine.

Absorption maximum: In the ultraviolet region (cf. Curve II, Fig. 1). Measurements were made at 410 $m\mu$.

Pyridine concentration: 5 c.c. in a total volume of 25 c.c., made up with water.

Reagent concentration: An increase in the rate of colour development was noticed with 2 c.c. of the reagent solution. Thus the maximum absorption of a solution containing 1 γ Co/c.c. was observed after 15 minutes with 2 c.c. of the reagent, while about half an hour was required for the same with 1 c.c. of the reagent. Further addition of the reagent solution was found to have no effect on the rate of colour development.

Sodium hydroxide concentration: The optical density of the complex solution was almost unaffected by a very dilute sodium hydroxide solution. But with a fairly strong solution (*N/4*) the absorption gradually increased with time, and the colour changed slowly from orange-yellow to yellowish brown. This is probably due to the conversion of the cobaltous compound into one of a higher valency state.

Beer's Law.—The system was found to obey Beer's law in presence of sodium acetate (cf. Curve II, Fig. 2). The optical density measurements were made after 30 minutes from the addition of the reagent.

Stability of the colour.—The optical density of solutions, prepared without sodium acetate, showed increasing values with time. In presence of sodium acetate, however, the maximum colour intensity was reached within half an hour after addition of the reagent. The optical density of such solutions was found to remain constant for 2-3 hours at the room temperature.

Sensitivity: 0.003 γ Co/cm² (S) and 0.0025 γ Co/cm² (p).

Effect of diverse ions (cf. under copper).—It is possible to eliminate the interferences caused by copper and nickel by means of potassium cyanide solution added after the development of maximum colour. Potassium cyanide discharges the colour

due to copper and nickel, without appreciably affecting that of cobalt. The optical density is to be measured after one hour from the addition of potassium cyanide. This ensures the complete discharge of the colour due to copper and nickel. In the presence of foreign ions a stronger solution of the reagent is to be used. It can be prepared by dissolving 0.25 g. of *NN'*-diphenylrubeanic acid in 50 c.c. of 2*N*-NaOH solution. 2 c.c. of this solution was used when both copper and nickel were present in the sample solution. 5 c.c. of potassium cyanide solution has been found to be sufficient for solutions containing 1 p.p.m. Co, in the presence of 30 p.p.m. Ni or 10 p.p.m. Cu.

Procedure.—To an almost neutral test solution 1 c.c. of 1% sodium acetate solution and 5 c.c. of pyridine were added. This was diluted to about 20 c.c. and treated with 2 c.c. of the reagent solution. The volume was then made up to 25 c.c. with water and the optical density measured at 410 $m\mu$ after 15-20 minutes. A reagent blank was always used for measurements. In presence of copper or nickel, precautions noted above should be taken.

Determination of Nickel

The following solutions were used: Standard nickel solution, 0.05 mg./c.c. All other solutions were the same as those used for the cobalt determination.

Absorption maximum: 510 $m\mu$ at which measurements were made (cf. Curve III, Fig 1).

An excess of pyridine or reagent solution had no effect on the colour intensity (cf. under cobalt).

NaOH concentration: Very dilute sodium hydroxide solution was without any appreciable effect on the optical density of the complex solution; but an excess of the alkali solution was found to diminish the intensity of the colour. Thus for 2 p.p.m. Co, 5 c.c. of *N/2* sodium hydroxide diminished the intensity by about 20%.

Beer's Law.—The system obeyed Beer's law (cf. Curve III, Fig. 2). At higher concentrations of nickel (>4 p.p.m.), presence of sodium acetate was helpful for the rapid development of the maximum colour intensity.

Stability of the colour: About 15-20 minutes were required for the attainment of maximum colour intensity. This time lag was more noticeable at higher concentrations of Co (>4 p.p.m.). About 2% increase in absorption was observed after 20 hours at the room temperature.

Sensitivity: 0.0075 γ Ni/cm² (S) and 0.03 γ Ni/cm² (p).

Effect of diverse ions: (cf. under copper and cobalt).

Procedure.—Pyridine (5 c.c.) was added to the test solution, which was almost neutral and free from interfering ions. This was followed by 10 c.c. of water and then 3 c.c. of the reagent solution. The mixture was shaken well for about 2-3 minutes and the volume made up to 25 c.c. with distilled water. After half an hour the optical density of the pink-red solution was measured at 510 $m\mu$ against a reagent blank. A solution of sodium acetate (1 c.c. of 1%) can be added before adding the reagent solution for the rapid development of colour.

Determination of Palladium

The following solutions were used: Standard palladium solution (0.05 mg. Pd per c.c.) and the reagent solution as for cobalt.

Absorption maximum: At about 395 $m\mu$ at which measurements were made (cf. Curve IV, Fig. 1).

Pyridine concentration: 5 c.c. in a total volume of 25 c.c., made up with water.

Reagent concentration: 1 c.c. of the reagent for Pd up to 0.1 mg. in 25 c.c. final volume.

NaOH concentration: An excess of the alkali retards the colour development. Thus with 5 c.c. of $N/4$ sodium hydroxide solution the maximum colour intensity was developed only after half an hour.

Beer's Law.—The system was found to obey Beer's law (cf. Curve III, Fig. 2). For palladium concentration more than 4 p.p.m., 3 c.c. of the reagent were added instead of 1 c.c.

Stability of the colour.—The colour was produced instantaneously on adding the reagent solution, and was stable for more than 24 hours at the room temperature.

Sensitivity: 0.0075 γ Pd/cm² (S) and 0.025 γ Pd/cm² (P).

Procedure.—To the palladium solution, which was separated from the interfering ions, 5 c.c. of pyridine, 5 c.c. of water and 1-3 c.c. (depending upon the palladium concentration) of the reagent solution were added in the order given. The volume was finally made up to 25 c.c. with water and the optical density^o measured at 395 $m\mu$ against a reagent blank.

Detection of Ruthenium

Ruthenium solutions, when warmed with NN' -diphenylrubeanic acid, develop a greenish blue coloration. But the precipitation of the complex occurs within a short time. However, it was possible to detect small amounts of ruthenium in the following manner: To the sample solution 2 c.c. of a mixture (1:1) of ethyl alcohol (95%) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (11N), and 1 c.c. of 0.01% alcoholic solution of the reagent were added. The mixture was warmed on a water-bath for about 5 minutes. A greenish yellow or a light green colour developed when ruthenium was present. The test was carried out in comparison with a blank containing the same amount of the reagent solution. By this means 0.06 γ Ru could be identified at a concentration limit of $1:5 \times 10^7$.